

Bringing PBL to Philippines's higher education: How much are teachers geared for the transition from traditional to PBL approach?

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Abstract

A teacher's teaching philosophy is the Northern star for directing their practices. Different teachers have their own views of effective routes for their students' academic achievement and thus follow different teaching approaches in delivering courses. Project-based learning (PBL) is constantly gaining popularity in computing and engineering education, especially in Western education systems. However, this approach is still preliminary in the Philippines, and the transition from the traditional to PBL is still challenging for educators of this region, where most of the teaching is still very much teacher-centered and lecture-based. This study explores the compatibility and mismatches between Computing and Engineering teachers' teaching philosophies and principles of PBL approach. The teaching philosophies are investigated through the two lenses of Behaviorism and Constructivism. The participants are non-PBL practitioners from different universities and colleges in the Philippines who have the desire to deliver PBL in Computing and Engineering courses for the first time. The study is conducted with mixed methods utilizing a survey followed by an in-depth interview, which cover the participants' (1) belief of learners, (2) curriculum flexibility, (3) teaching-learning activities, (4) teachers' roles and (5) assessment in comparison with the commonalities of PBL approach. The survey's data analyzed in SPSS showed that the participants leaned more on the side of constructivism in their belief of teaching and learning; however, the analysis of interviews in NVivo revealed different degrees the teachers stuck to Behaviorism or Constructivism as regards teacher's role, learning style, and assessment in different parts of their teaching.

Keywords: project-based learning, teaching philosophy, constructivism, behaviorism.

1 Introduction

Teaching practice is guided by beliefs in effective teaching and learning. Such beliefs are formed from teachers' learning experiences, teaching experiences, observation of good teaching practice, as well as exposure to academic workshops, conferences and trainings. Also, different disciplines may have discrepant effective teaching practices. In computing and engineering education programs, course content and teaching methods are required to be constantly updated to keep up with the shifting sands of the word of technology. Among various teaching methods, PBL is widely recognized as effective for education in this field; however, whether this drastic approach is challenging to cultures appreciating rote learning is questionable. PBL is a teaching-learning approach, stemming from constructivism (Jumaat, Tasir, Halim, & Ashari, 2017), which assists independent and autonomous learners to resolve real-life problems in authentic projects (Krajcik, Czermiak, & Berger, 1999). It fosters active, collaborative learning, individualization of learning, and intrinsic motivation of learning to satisfy self-inquisitiveness with the assistance or facilitation of teachers (Chua, 2014; Orevi & Dannon, 1999). The emphasis put on self-discovery of knowledge by self-learning and learning in groups corresponds to the core principles of constructivist learning theory.

On the contrary, for Eastern context, (Subramaniam, 2008) favored the idea that most Asian students try to keep a harmonious atmosphere, avoid raising individual voices, consider teachers as distributors of knowledge, and evaluators of their learning. In such learning environments, the constructivist approach would find a slim chance to fit in (Bekerman, 2001).

Generally, it is expected that education in the region will be characterized by teacher-centered classrooms (Campbell & Yong, 1993), an emphasis on extrinsic motivation (Young-Ihm, 2002), and a focus on “drill-like approaches” (Agarkar & Brock, 2017). However, there has been a shift to encourage more student-centered classrooms in Asia (Hallinger & Lu, 2013), even in places with a long tradition of teacher-centeredness, product-based teaching, and students’ passiveness (Braine, 2003). The movement away from Behaviorism in Asian education has been clearly proved with the rarity of research publications mentioning teacher-centered instructions in this region in the recent literature. However, the comparison between the present level of teachers’ remaining application of this teaching method and the scope of their implementation of constructivist approach has not drawn much attention. Obviously, these two teaching approaches are quite contradicting and can hardly tolerate each other in the same delivery. Thus, this creates a paradox-like situation in the Philippines where the Behaviorism is deeply rooted in the educational system while that very system is in the mandate to transform to a Constructivist era, especially for the application of PBL in computing and engineering education. As part of the research project to introduce PBL approach into Colleges and Universities in the Philippines, this study investigates the compatibility between teachers’ teaching philosophies according to Behaviorism and Constructivism in accordance with the principles of PBL approach. The findings of this study will answer the following research questions: (1) To what extent are the teaching philosophies of Philippines university lecturers compatible with Constructivism? (2) To what extent are the teaching philosophies of Philippines university lecturers compatible with PBL principles?

The result then serves as an orientation for intervention in the action research that manages to conduct PBL courses for computing and engineering courses in selected colleges and universities in the Philippines.

2 Background Theories

2.1 Teaching Philosophy

Teaching philosophy is defined as “a systematic and critical rationale that focuses on the important components defining effective teaching and learning in a particular discipline and/or institutional context” (Schönwetter, Sokal, Friesen, & Taylor, 2002). There goes a proverb: ‘The teacher has not taught until the student has learned’. Therefore, before developing a teaching philosophy statement normally come discussions of teachers’ belief in how learning actually takes place. However, there are slight differences in the components of a teaching philosophy statement following the teacher’s belief of teaching and learning. A teaching philosophy statement as considered to be composed of learning models, teaching models, and assessment (Eierman, 2008), but learning goals, teaching methods, learning assessment, and teaching assessment (Kearns & Sullivan, 2011), or conceptualization of learning, conceptualization of teaching, goals for students’ learning, the implementation of the philosophy and personal growth plan (Chism, 1998), and conceptualization of learning, conceptualization of an effective teaching and learning environment, expectations of the student–teacher relationship, student assessment, and assessment of learning goals (Owens, Miller, & Grise-Owens, 2014).

As can be seen, common concerns can be found in teachers’ belief of learning serving as a foundation for the teaching and learning activities, the organization of curriculum, the roles of teachers, and the design of assessment to favor learning. However, in this study, the teaching philosophy is used as reference checklist for comparison of Behaviorism against Constructivism and PBL approach, which embrace quite contrasting views of learners. Therefore, the teachers’ beliefs of learners should also be included in the following review of the two learning theories.

2.2 Behaviorism vs Constructivism as foundation for teaching practices

The Table 1 compares and contrasts the two learning theories following the aforementioned components of teaching philosophy statements to lay the foundation for more insight into the status quo of PBL education in the Philippines’ Universities.

Table 1. Behaviorism vs constructivism as the foundation of teaching practices.

	Behaviorism	Constructivism
Teachers' belief of learning	Teachers consider learning as a change in behaviour in response to stimuli, and this happens in students' observation, exposure to teachers' explanation, and practice with teachers' feedback and motivation (Fosnot, 2013). Learning is achieved when a desired response is given to a target stimulus (Ertmer & Newby, 1993).	Teachers conceptualize learning as the active interaction of learners to the surrounding physical and social environment to interpret and reinterpret their understanding of the world (Fosnot, 2013). Learning occurs when one constructs both mechanisms for learning and his or her own unique version of the knowledge, colored by background, experiences, and aptitudes (Roblyer & Doering, 2012).
Teachers' belief of learners (Ertmer & Newby, 1993).	Students take a passive role in receiving knowledge by reacting to the stimuli	Students are expected to actively search for knowledge and validate their understanding through collaboration and communication with relevant people.
Teaching activities	Teaching is to (1) select the cue to gain target responses from students; (2) develop the proper practice to elicit desired responses; and (3) set up situations with stimuli to get students' response and then give them feedback for reinforcement (Groppe, 1987).	Teaching is to guide students in their meaning making, and in self-monitoring, evaluating and updating meaning construction. Also, teachers need to create real-life situations for students to experience (Ertmer & Newby, 1993).
Teachers' roles	Teachers are knowledge transmitters (Scheurman, 1998).	Teachers are facilitators or collaborators (Scheurman, 1998).
The organization of curriculum	The curriculum is predetermined, divided into small tasks and arranged in an increasingly complex order (Fosnot, 2013).	Curriculum comprises tasks that are complex and authentic (Applefield, Huber, & Moallem, 2000).
The design of assessment	Criterion-referenced assessment (Ertmer & Newby, 1993) which is the assessment comparing learners' performance with a set of criteria to decide whether they pass or fail the test (Clifford, 2016).	Assessment tests students' knowledge and their application of knowledge in solving problems (Ertmer & Newby, 1993).

2.3 PBL Principles

Project-based learning approach is an instructional approach encouraging students to be autonomous learners to carry out their authentic projects (Krajcik et al., 1999). However, according to (Heitmann, 1996) PBL approaches can be divided into two versions: "project-organized curriculum" and "project-oriented studies". The former is described as a mixture between other methods of instructions and PBL approach with small projects for each course, which are built up to the final project before university graduation; whereas, the latter

is probably unconnected project work in each course. In the condition of the Philippines higher education, where PBL courses are still not common, it is expected that the project-oriented studies are reasonable for universities that apply PBL for the first time. However, regardless of whatever version of PBL is used, in many cases, the PBL approach is laid on the foundation of constructivism (Chu, Tse, Loh, & Chow, 2011; Seet & Quek, 2010) with the following principles.

As regards the mechanism of learning, PBL looks at learning as a process of students' responding to the task to construct knowledge through social interaction based on their previous knowledge and experience (Seet & Quek, 2010). Learning occurs when students can use their schema – their individual accumulated understanding of the world - to interpret and comprehend the relevant knowledge taught to them. The bridge between what is already known and what is new and reasonably challenging should be done in the zone of proximal development where, according to (Vygotsky, 1978), students can reach their potential levels of development after exceeding their actual levels thanks to the scaffolding of more capable peers or the teacher. In practice, project-based learning is fulfilled through individual research and group work to complete the project (Perrenet, Bouhuijs, & Smits, 2000). Indeed, after the project has been given to a team, students have to divide workload to each team member and work on the given tasks individually. However, because of the complex nature of the project, the collaboration among different students, and between students with teachers and local experts is essential for the investigation and realization of the artefact as claimed by Marx, Blumenfeld, Krajcik and Soloway (1997).

As for teachers' roles, teaching in PBL courses, teachers rarely give pure lectures, but predominantly act as facilitators (Blumenfeld et al., 1991; Chua, 2014). The final goal of teaching is to help individual students to construct their own knowledge through meaning making which is aided by exchanges and guidance of friends and teachers. As regards in-class activities, inquiries will unveil some certain areas of knowledge that need addressing for further learning in the course. As for presentations, teachers play a crucial role in discovering challenges of student groups to either guide them through to the solutions or match groups for cross assistance. Also, sometimes students construct incorrect understanding of the issue and show problems that need troubleshooting. These difficulties prove the necessity of tutorials for student groups (Perrenet et al., 2000) where evaluation of the project progress and solution to technical or group management problems are figured out. The most striking teaching activities in PBL approach, therefore, can be concentrating on lectures for introducing new concepts, presentations moderation for assessing students' work and providing feedback, and group tutorials for troubleshooting students' challenges, especially technical problems.

For learning styles, PBL is largely learner-centered, so it upholds the "considerable individualization of curriculum" (Moursund, 1998). The content of a PBL course is therefore developed from the learning needs of students to complete their assigned projects and is also guided by the learning outcomes of the course and the program as a whole. The teachers' project selection is, therefore, of utmost importance for the success of the course because either too challenging or too easy projects will render students bored with learning. Also, the intricacy of projects sometimes requires the combination of expertise of two or more disciplines (Mills & Treagust, 2003), which improves students' experience of how different knowledge should be integrated in real-life work.

When it comes to assessment, PBL approach assesses not only academic but also non-academic skills (Chua, 2014) to gear students towards working in authentic projects currently demanded by the industry. Assessment, therefore, is designed to evaluate the academic performance of students together with their manipulation of soft skills in group work and communication with related agents for their projects. To do so, a multi-component assessment scheme is required to include students' presentations, peer evaluation, learning journals, quizzes, and the final artefact itself. In that manner, PBL courses are mainly equipped with formative assessment (Bell, 2010; Montequín, Fernández, Balsera, & Nieto, 2013). Additionally, the use of rubrics is recommended since they provide students with clear expectations of outcomes and clarifies criteria for assessment as emphasized by (Grant, 2011).

3 Methodology

The researcher performed a structured survey and interview to obtain the quantitative and qualitative understanding of the compatibility and mismatches between Computing and Engineering teachers' teaching philosophies and principles of PBL approach.

24 non-PBL practitioners in selected colleges and universities in the Philippines were identified by the researchers. All non-PBL practitioners are teaching in computing and engineering. Cronbach alpha will be applied to validate the reliability of the questionnaire.

The survey is adapted from (Zinn, 1990) investigating teachers' beliefs about learners (items 11 and 12), beliefs about the purpose of education (item 3), belief about content (items 1 and 5), and beliefs about the learning process (items 2, 4, 9, and 15). Items about the instructional process and the role of educators (items 6, 7, 8, 10, 13, and 14). The questions about Constructivism are based on literature review of that learning theory as presented above. The data from the survey will be analyzed using paired t-test for each category.

A follow-up interview was conducted upon 5 participants whose belief, according to the survey result, fell into the category of behaviorism. The in-depth interview showed the participants' rationale as to why and how they are practicing behaviorism. The interview will focus on five (5) points: belief of learners, teaching activities, teachers' roles, curriculum flexibility, and focus of assessment (on academic skill only in tests or also include soft skills in presentations, and students' portfolio). The data will be analyzed in NVIVO to bring forward the highlights of the teachers' beliefs and current practice in comparison with the fundamentals of PBL approach.

Finally, recommendations were presented to future researchers to introduce PBL methodologies to the participants.

4 Research Findings

4.1. Survey Results

Table 2 shows the reliability of the questionnaire exploring the conformity of teaching philosophies of non-PBL practitioners in the Philippines and the principles of behaviorism and constructivism. The differences are evaluated using the two-tailed test statistical method.

Table 2. Comparison between behaviorism and constructivism.

Teachers' Belief Criterion	Cronbach Alpha α	t-value	p-value
Beliefs about the learning process	.969	-.10057	.780655
Beliefs about the content	.965	.15695	.7818965
Belief about the purpose of education	.929	.2262	.822045
The instructional process and the role of educators	.984	-.00198	.848725
Teachers' belief about learners	.786	-.79912	.45545

Table 3. Cronbach alpha interpretation.

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha > 0.9$	Excellent

$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Cronbach alpha was used to check the reliability of the questionnaire. The result shows that all items per criterion received an excellent reliability, except item "Teachers' Belief About Learner" ($\alpha = 0.786$). The result of Teachers' Belief About Learner has an acceptable internal consistency based on Table 3. This identifies the question's reliability as "acceptable" or "fair" and can be interpreted as to how the respondents understood the learner's role while in a student-centered environment.

The foundations of the practices for teaching were identified as either behaviourism or constructivism, which can be seen in Table 1. Six factors were used as the criteria, namely: teachers' belief of learning, teachers' belief of learners, teaching activities, teachers' roles, organization of curriculum and design of assessment. Using t-test with a critical value of $p < 0.05$, the p-value obtained was based on the probability of a null hypothesis, which identifies the teacher as a behaviorist, versus that of an alternative hypothesis, where a teacher leans more towards a constructivist. The results were taken from the survey conducted using the adapted questions from Zinn (1990), identifying two varying degrees of the participants' inclination toward each of the two teaching methodologies. Based on p-value result in Table 2, the participants had identified the following criteria as mostly the same with their personal teaching practice: (1) learning process, (2) content, (3) purpose of education, (4) instructional process and role of educators. This result was used to determine the correlation of each criterion to one another. It should be pointed out, however, that the t-value is smaller than the value on the degree of freedom chart; this means Behaviorism and Constructivism is understood to be significantly different.

The teaching philosophies of the participants were identified mostly under constructivism, which were also aligned with their understanding of the PBL principle's use of a project-oriented studies approach. Likewise, it can be said that few were familiar with project-organized curriculum and would only partially apply to professional courses which are specifically intended for capstone project's preparation but not for the entire curriculum. Because of this, with the mechanisms of learning, students are constrained to working within their own course. Collaboration and social interaction are limited to specific groups which would often change per course. As evidently shown on Table 2 results where belief on the learning process, content, and purpose of education are identified as somehow correlated in defining how projects are developed.

4.2 Interview Results

Based on the interviews, the teacher's role, learning style and modes of assessment are still considered mixed between the two teaching methods. Participants still deliver pure lectures, mixed with facilitator roles during hands-on activities. Because of this, the learning style is also mixed as either teacher-centered during pure lecture days, to student-centred during classroom activities. Indicative of the results as shown in Figure 1, the Teacher's Role and Teaching Activities come out as Very Positive and Very Negative, indicating extreme identified beliefs showing a big difference on how the participants understand and practice PBL. The correlation between the teacher's role and activities signify how it affects the participants' decision in designing and delivering teaching and learning activities. Assessments are based on a fixed syllabus given for each course. The modes of assessment given are mostly summative in the form of quizzes and exams, with projects and activities identified to be formative, measuring technical skills, as well as soft skills, such as communication. However, participants still identify that knowledge comes from the teacher, making the classroom setup as teacher-centered, with activities given to students after a lecture. The interviewees also agreed that a student's

role (belief of learners) and how and what they learn (belief of learning) is related to the design of the curriculum and the assessment given to them. This is again indicative of how the Philippine education system is based on a set curriculum.

Figure 1. Nvivo interview result

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The Philippines educators' vision to uplift the current state of economy is very clear and orientation of PBL in the educational system can take up this vision (Tiangco, 2005). And in this study, 19 out of 24 participants from different Philippine universities were identified to be focusing more on constructivism. Though the approaches in teaching computing and engineering discipline for the participants signify that they are transitioning from teacher-based approach to a learner-based system. This is due to the fact that in every Philippine University setting, it starts with the curriculum where program outcomes are identified, to the course syllabi where learning outcomes are then derived. This then translates to the teaching activities and design of assessments to validate if said outcomes have been met. However, a teacher's role and how their students are supposed to learn is identified still on the behaviorist point-of-view where students are expected to be passive listeners to teachers who deliver lectures.

The philosophies in teaching computing and engineering of teachers leaning more on constructivism and those sticking more to behaviorism are similar in terms of the beliefs about the learning process, content and purpose of education as shown in Table 2. Though teachers still believe that they are knowledge providers rather than facilitators that lead students to the solution to the problem. The teacher expects the learners to acquire knowledge through the education process. Improving the aptitude of learners to sustain, nurture and cultivate the students to harness their potentials through their maturation process (de Leon-Carillo, 2007). Learning occurs through the process of constructing the artefacts, so the end product is critical to the learning goals (Grant, 2011; Prince & Felder, 2006). Teachers have a clear intention to meet students' needs by means of class activities and motivate students' learning.

While teachers' role is still that of being a knowledge provider rather than a facilitator, teachers have clear intention to guide students' learning by providing class activities that motivate students' learning in the process. This is shown in Figure 1 from the Teachers' role and Teaching Activities results, which has very negative and very positive results respectively. The result identifies how the Constructivist participant and the Behaviorist participant have very different beliefs when it comes to PBL.

In conclusion, although the Computing and Engineering programs at most Phillipine universities still quite strongly adhere to behaviorism with fixed curricula, quizzes and tests, teacher roles and student roles. But it can be noted that the approach is shifting from teacher-based to learner-centered based on the outcome of the study, that: (1) while behaviorist and constructivist differ in opinion on how learning is delivered, based from the six factors, there is no significant difference with regards to desired knowledge gained by its learners;

(2) while teachers are considered the prime source of knowledge in Philippine setting (de Leon-Carillo, 2007), the teaching philosophies of the participants were identified mostly as under constructivism; and (3) Philippine universities are seen to be transitioning from being teacher-based to embracing PBL beliefs, such as defining student learning outcomes, identifying the roles of teachers as facilitators, use of rubrics and small project collaborations.

With this, it can be said that the openness in using PBL in Computing and Engineering programs can prove to be vital in the readiness of the students to enter the real-work life experience as mentored by their teachers.

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